

The effects of COVID-19 on the priorities of the topic associated with community-based activities and citizen participation

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Keywords: community-based; citizen participation

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6849627

Editorial

Citizen participation is one of the approaches on which New Public Management and New Public Governance are based and can be qualified as a community-based tool in the management of public administration or common goods (Strokosch & Osborne, 2020; Brescia, 2020; Secinaro et al., 2022). As a result of COVID-19, Europe may have changed and has identified new strands, approaches, and concepts that require the attention of scholars. Therefore, the analysis of reality can provide a greater vision in a stormy period than the analysis of academic literature alone could give. If in the business, management, and economics sector, we have a restructuring of approaches, systems, and contexts (Campra, Esposito & Brescia, 2020). The expectation is that there will be changes and priorities also in public participation that are different from those identified in the literature (Massaro et al., 2021). Therefore, from the results of NEXIS UNI, news, law, and business database (Knap, 2018), all the results have been identified in the magazines from 2021 to 2022 in which we talk about citizen participation, public participation, and citizen involvement. The identification of the times focused on the context of European sources and news only. The analysis identified and eliminated the duplicates, with 2529 results in English and Italian. The content analysis conducted allows, with an objective method, to identify the primary key concepts (Secinaro et al., 2021). The software adopted for the analysis of the results is LEXIMANCER, which allowed the grouping based on the frequency with which the concepts appear in the text and the significance of the relationship of the elements expressed. Significance in the relationship between concepts also defines relationships and representation (Smith & Humphreys, 2006; Dal Mas, 2019; Secinaro et al., 2021a). By analyzing the texts extracted from the research on NEXIS UNI and the software, it was possible to define figure 1.

The government cluster is associated with several micro-themes, including social networks associated with the government and outline specific attention that must be given to the needs expressed on social networks, needs that must be mediated and managed by society, and by politics that must be able to rework them. Many states and local authorities use digital platforms to provide information on significant events creating the basis for having a community app used later to receive flows from the citizen and give feedback. At the same time, the relationship between government and younger citizens remains, representing 65% of those who use social media and need appropriate dialogue and comparison approaches. Among other micro terms, the international report in which post covid the European Forum is the first forum for discussion to define the new guidelines at the national level. New attention has been paid to the population's health by focusing on certain issues such as air quality and continuous surveillance by the World Health Organization at the request of citizens and citizens' organizations. In international relations, the return of the attention given to the budget and the spending authorization process involves the issue of the budget for war refugees. Among the other macro-themes of elections, in which community-based activities are the most active in the process of reform processes, it is precisely the groups of citizens who can protest to develop a genuinely democratic local context. Another macro-theme that can be identified among spontaneous groups of citizens is that of sustainable finance geared more to erasing inequalities, also associated with the management and management aspect of the courts with a pressure to change the approach of judges by increasing technologies and changing the law concerning the evolution of the social context. Sweden continues the democratization process of the rest of the world as well. The last issue associated with the government is COVID which has seen the need to involve the most significant number of people in the vaccination process; this has entailed on the one hand, the launch of a computerized and online management system, and on the same time the future need for innovative performance systems to evaluate intervention projects with such large dimensions.

Country

The attention of many countries continues to be focused on establishing anti-corruption systems. The issue is more significant following the amount of funding and decisions made by the various states during and after the spread of COVID-19. This theme is significantly associated with crimes and cases of money laundering through businesses. The change in the legal system and attention to forms of control over the financing of terrorism requires the involvement of citizens. Another significant issue concerns the protection and rights of immigrants and war refugees. Among the main clusters associated with the country, the word government with the search by the European Community for new policies aimed at equality between women and men.

Local

Citizen involvement is required in particular on aspects that have become significant in recent years, including the relationship between well-being and healthy eating. Furthermore, the pandemic crisis has brought out the difficulty in managing the services that currently deal with mental problems. The analysis is required to identify new approaches to crisis management, risk management, and involvement of family work activities to reduce the number of suicides.

Place

Among the most virtuous states oriented to citizen participation and attention to the needs of the community, we can find Spain, which tries to identify, thanks to a collaborative approach, the best possibilities to face climate change and the use of water in collaboration with the World Meteorological Organization also through the construction of a standard information system. The presentation of the results in Sweden plays a role in promoting good practices around the world.

Rights

The analysis identifies the human rights following the war in Russia among the main topics addressed. In particular, freedom of speech and protest are the main issues in the Russian territory, where the inhabitants suffer a double limitation of movement within the borders. In particular, through its agents and other means, Russia has initiated the persecution of those who are against the regime by eliminating political opponents and NGO leaders.

To promote rights, the House of Citizens identifies as a model not only the elected subjects but also professionals (academics, scientists, businessmen, and artists) among the subjects to be involved in bringing about social change.

Body

The issue of rights is associated with that of the protection of the body in particular projects and benefits that should be more developed for disabled people.

Projects

Projects involving cities aimed at becoming smart can change the currently active system, and new models of involvement and public consultations are also needed to involve citizens. France is the leading country currently interested in addressing the issue, last year through "Best Practice for Citizen Engagement" carried out in Barcelona (Spain).

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